

Two Qubits Permutation Symmetry: Simple Proofs

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Exchange symmetry of two qubits is fundamental in quantum information and computation. There are varieties of qubits applicable in quantum information, their role of exchange symmetry play an important role in developing quantum applications. Here in the present paper, we give two alternative proofs for the exchange symmetry of two qubits. We show, the exchange symmetry of two qubits preserve under Unitary and Hermitian operations both, it does not matter whether the qubits are indistinguishable or distinguishable particles.

I. INTRODUCTION

Quantum computing is a promising research area that deals with the merger of theoretical computer science and quantum mechanics. Quantum computing relies upon the quantum phenomena of entanglement [1, 2] and superposition to perform operations. But quantum systems are too evasive such that they may loose their entanglement can pass through sudden death of entanglement [3–6], which must be protected. There exists several postulates in quantum theory which enclose the superposition principle and mandate unitary evolutions [7–9]. The postulates are (i) The state of quantum system is formulated in terms of state vectors. (ii) The evolutions of quantum systems are unitary. (iii) the outcomes are limited to orthonormal set of vectors for some measurement [10]. (iv) every measurement can be verified in the sense that immediate repetition of measurement produces the same result [11]. (v) the probability of measuring a given state is calculated as the squared modulus of the amplitude attached with that state. A composite quantum system can persist entanglement and more than one measurement outcomes are possible for some kind of computation [12]. The measurement of composite quantum system compels it to select from a finite set of orthogonal states [13]. The state of composite system is formulated by a density operator in suitable Hilbert space \mathcal{H} . Suppose the composite quantum system ($S^{AB\dots}$) consists subsystems (A, B, \dots), then the structure is defined as the tensor product of respective Hilbert spaces such as

$$\mathcal{H}^{AB\dots} = \mathcal{H}^A \otimes \mathcal{H}^B \otimes \dots \quad (1)$$

In general, consider an arbitrary state $|\psi_{AB}\rangle$ in the tensor product space $\mathcal{H}^A \otimes \mathcal{H}^B$:

$$|\psi_{AB}\rangle = \sum_{i,j} \alpha_{ij} |\phi_i\rangle_A \otimes |\varphi_j\rangle_B \quad (2)$$

where $|\phi_i\rangle$ is basis for \mathcal{H}_A and $|\varphi_j\rangle$ is basis for \mathcal{H}_B respectively. A tensor product (\otimes) is a mathematical operation that combines two Hilbert spaces to form another Hilbert space. It can be noted that the dimension of whole system increases exponentially with the number of subsystems e.g. a 10-subsystem has a Hilbert space of dimensionality $2^{10} = 1024$. A tensor product operation is central to describe the demonstration of composite quantum systems. It is called as homogeneous if it consists equal dimension of subsystems, else heterogeneous [14]. Although, the tensor product operation between subsystems is not commutative in nature i.e. $|m\rangle \otimes |n\rangle \neq |n\rangle \otimes |m\rangle$. Therefore, the states $|\psi_{12}\rangle$ and $|\psi_{21}\rangle$ are definite when it can be described as states in \mathbb{C}^N . Any state $|\psi_{AB}\rangle$ is said to be preserve the exchange symmetry if it is identical to $|\psi_{BA}\rangle$. Under transformation, the state $|\psi\rangle$ is called as exchange invariant if it remains invariant such as

$$|\psi_{AB}\rangle \rightarrow |\psi_{BA}\rangle \quad (3)$$

Although, the state $|\psi_{AB}\rangle$ is equivalent to $|\psi_{BA}\rangle$ if the expectation value of any operator (\hat{O}) is similar in states [15] i.e.

$$\langle \psi_{AB} | \hat{O} \otimes I | \psi_{AB} \rangle = \langle \psi_{BA} | I \otimes \hat{O} | \psi_{BA} \rangle \quad (4)$$

where I is the identity. The symmetric subspace for two qubits is spanned by Dicke basis [16]. In the last decade, the concept of symmetric states of homogeneous systems has got overwhelming response among research communities. It has been widely studied theoretically and experimentally by considering entanglement [15, 17, 18] and tomography [19, 20]. In quantum computational theory, entanglement is the backbone of many quantum algorithms. A pure quantum state (n - qubits) is called unentangled if it can be written as tensor product of states of the individual qubits. Otherwise, any state which cannot be written

in tensor product form is considered entangled. Multipartite entanglement is crucial in exploring the error detection [21], private sharing, quantum communication, dense coding and decoherence in quantum computers. The case of bipartite entanglement has been extensively examined [22, 23]. Although, there exists still many open problems which need to be addressed in future. Symmetry is considered as a basic tool to design models and to investigate systems without studying about its structure [24]. It has several practical applications such as widely used to observe the spectrum/structure of hydrogen atom or to classify the particle states in physics [25]. It is natural to examine the symmetry of entangled systems. Indeed, exchange symmetry is pivotal to get the identical distributed and independent properties of subsystems [26]. In this paper, we proved that the exchange symmetry of two qubits under Unitary and Hermitian operations is intact, it does not matter whether the qubits are indistinguishable or distinguishable particles. The organization of the paper is as follows: In section II, a procedure to preserve the exchange symmetry by considering the case of unitary and hermitian matrices is given. We examined the case of entanglement of states in Section III, followed by a conclusion in Section IV.

II. SIMPLE PROOFS

Assume two particles (1,2) having composite wave function $|\psi_{12}\rangle$. Let exchange both the particles (2,1), now the composite wave function is $|\psi_{21}\rangle$. Our goal is to show that after applying the Unitary/Hermitian Matrices the composite wave function remain same as below,

$$|\psi_{12}\rangle = |\psi_{21}\rangle \quad (5)$$

A. Case 1: Unitary matrices

Applying the Unitary operation on composite state (1,2), we get,

$$U|\psi_{12}\rangle = \lambda_1|\psi_{12}\rangle \quad (6)$$

Applying the Unitary operation on composite state (2,1)

$$U|\psi_{21}\rangle = \lambda_2|\psi_{21}\rangle \quad (7)$$

The state $|\psi_{21}\rangle$ can be obtained by applying the exchange operator on $|\psi_{12}\rangle$, Let assume the arbitrary operator is \hat{O} , than we can write,

$$\hat{O}|\psi_{12}\rangle = |\psi_{21}\rangle \quad (8)$$

Multiplying the Eq (6) both sided by the operator \hat{O} , we obtain,

$$\hat{O}U|\psi_{12}\rangle = \lambda_1\hat{O}|\psi_{12}\rangle \quad (9)$$

Putting the value from Eq. (8), we obtain,

$$\hat{O}U|\psi_{12}\rangle = \lambda_1|\psi_{21}\rangle \quad (10)$$

multiplying both the sided by U^\dagger we get

$$(U^\dagger\hat{O}U)|\psi_{12}\rangle = \lambda_1U^\dagger|\psi_{21}\rangle \quad (11)$$

It is known that unitary operations leave the state unchanged so $(U^\dagger\hat{O}U) = \hat{O}$, so we can write,

$$\hat{O}|\psi_{12}\rangle = \lambda_1U^\dagger|\psi_{21}\rangle \quad (12)$$

rewriting the above equation, we get

$$\hat{O}|\psi_{12}\rangle = U^\dagger(\lambda_1|\psi_{21}\rangle) \quad (13)$$

Putting the value of $|\psi_{21}\rangle$ from Eq. (7) in Eq. (13) we obtain,

$$\hat{O}|\psi_{12}\rangle = U^\dagger(\lambda_1(\frac{1}{\lambda_2}U|\psi_{21}\rangle)) \quad (14)$$

$$= \frac{\lambda_1}{\lambda_2}U^\dagger U|\psi_{21}\rangle \quad (15)$$

We know

$$U^\dagger U = U U^\dagger = I$$

So we get

$$\hat{O}|\psi_{12}\rangle = \frac{\lambda_1}{\lambda_2}|\psi_{21}\rangle \quad (16)$$

We need to prove that the Unitary Operator (U) must preserve the symmetry, so in this case $\hat{O} = U$

So applying this condition in Eq (16). We further obtain,

$$U|\psi_{12}\rangle = \frac{\lambda_1}{\lambda_2}|\psi_{21}\rangle \quad (17)$$

The symmetry will be preserve if and only if $\frac{\lambda_1}{\lambda_2} = 1$, if this satisfy than we can have

$$U|\psi_{12}\rangle = 1.|\psi_{21}\rangle \quad (18)$$

$$U|\psi_{12}\rangle = |\psi_{21}\rangle \quad (19)$$

Eq. (19) Concludes that Unitary operators preserve the symmetry if and only if $\frac{\lambda_1}{\lambda_2} = 1$ So we need to prove $\frac{\lambda_1}{\lambda_2} = 1$. At this point we can start with the simplest case, assume a state of a single particle, which can be written as qubit as below,

$$|\psi_1\rangle = \alpha|0\rangle + \beta|1\rangle \quad (20)$$

Calculate it's norm (ie length), it is obtained as

$$norm_{|\psi_1\rangle} = \sqrt{\alpha^2 + \beta^2} \quad (21)$$

Find out the inner product of the state $|\psi_1\rangle$ with itself, so it is obtained as

$$\langle\psi_1|\psi_1\rangle = |\alpha|^2 + |\beta|^2 \quad (22)$$

So we can write the Eq (17) as

$$norm_{|\psi_1\rangle} = \sqrt{\langle\psi_1|\psi_1\rangle} \quad (23)$$

If qubit is normalized than

$$norm_{|\psi_1\rangle} = \sqrt{\langle\psi_1|\psi_1\rangle} = 1 \quad (24)$$

Simply it can also be shown for the states $|\psi_{12}\rangle$ or $|\psi_{21}\rangle$ than we can write

$$norm_{|\psi_{12}\rangle} = \sqrt{\langle\psi_{12}|\psi_{12}\rangle} \quad (25)$$

and similarly,

$$norm_{|\psi_{21}\rangle} = \sqrt{\langle\psi_{21}|\psi_{21}\rangle} \quad (26)$$

If the states $|\psi_{12}\rangle$ and $|\psi_{21}\rangle$ are normalized than, obviously we can have

$$norm_{|\psi_{12}\rangle} = \sqrt{\langle\psi_{12}|\psi_{12}\rangle} = 1 \quad (27)$$

Similarly,

$$norm_{|\psi_{21}\rangle} = \sqrt{\langle\psi_{21}|\psi_{21}\rangle} = 1 \quad (28)$$

Note that, norm is assumed as absolute value, so it is always positive, so for that reason sometimes we write in literature $||norm_{|\psi_{21}\rangle}|| = 1$, the sign $||\cdot||$ used for absolute value. Now, re-look at the Eq. (6), we have

$$U|\psi_{12}\rangle = \lambda_1|\psi_{12}\rangle \quad (29)$$

Taking the complex conjugate and transpose of both the sides, we get

$$\langle\psi_{12}|U^\dagger = \lambda_1^*\langle\psi_{12}| \quad (30)$$

Multiplying Eq. (29) on both the sides with U^\dagger

$$U^\dagger U|\psi_{12}\rangle = \lambda_1 U^\dagger|\psi_{12}\rangle \quad (31)$$

Multiplying both the sides with $\langle\psi_{12}|$, we get

$$\langle\psi_{12}|U^\dagger U|\psi_{12}\rangle = \lambda_1\langle\psi_{12}|U^\dagger|\psi_{12}\rangle \quad (32)$$

We know $UU^\dagger = U^\dagger U = I$, so we have

$$\langle\psi_{12}|I|\psi_{12}\rangle = \lambda_1\lambda_1^*\langle\psi_{12}|\psi_{12}\rangle \quad (33)$$

$I|\psi_{12}\rangle = I$, because identity operator do not change the state. Further we proceed,

$$\langle\psi_{12}|\psi_{12}\rangle = \lambda_1\lambda_1^*\langle\psi_{12}|\psi_{12}\rangle \quad (34)$$

Putting the values form Eq. (27), i have

$$||\lambda_1||^2 = \frac{\langle\psi_{12}|\psi_{12}\rangle}{\langle\psi_{12}|\psi_{12}\rangle} = \frac{1}{1} = 1 \quad (35)$$

$$\lambda_1 = \pm 1 \quad (36)$$

Similar proof can be carried out with the state $|\psi_{21}\rangle$ if it is normalised. Hence we can have

$$\lambda_2 = \pm 1 \quad (37)$$

Hence in the last we can have from the Eq. (17).

$$U|\psi_{12}\rangle = \frac{\lambda_1}{\lambda_2}|\psi_{21}\rangle = |\psi_{21}\rangle \quad (38)$$

$$U|\psi_{12}\rangle = |\psi_{21}\rangle \quad (39)$$

Similarly we can prove

$$U|\psi_{21}\rangle = |\psi_{12}\rangle \quad (40)$$

So, from Eq. (39) and (40), we conclude that applying the Unitary on either state ($|\psi_{12}\rangle, |\psi_{21}\rangle$) we get the state unchanged. More simplification we can do easily, looking at the Eq (39)

$$U|\psi_{12}\rangle = |\psi_{21}\rangle \quad (41)$$

$$U(|\psi_{12}\rangle - |\psi_{21}\rangle) = 0 \quad (42)$$

Here, $U \neq 0$, so we get

$$(|\psi_{12}\rangle - |\psi_{21}\rangle) = 0 \quad (43)$$

$$|\psi_{12}\rangle = |\psi_{21}\rangle \quad (44)$$

In the above equation we have proved the preservation of exchange symmetry. Similarly we can prove from Eq.(40), which shows that state remain unchanged after applying the unitary. So we have been proved that the Unitary operation preserve the exchange symmetry provided the composite state of the particles are normalized. This fact is obvious that we always work on normalized states.

B. Hermitian matrices

Now we try the same problem with Hermitian matrices. In previous proof, we have proved that the composite state must be normalized, than only Unitary operator preserve the symmetry. But here we pre-assumed that the composite state is normalized, because normalization is expected in Quantum mechanics while dealing with proper calculations. Let assume an arbitrary operator O which change the symmetry as follows,

$$\hat{O}|\psi_{12}\rangle = |\psi_{21}\rangle \quad (45)$$

Here, $\lambda = 1$, and state is assumed as normalized. Similarly,

$$\hat{O}|\psi_{21}\rangle = |\psi_{12}\rangle \quad (46)$$

Here again, $\lambda = 1$, and state is assumed as normalized. Both the Eqs. (45) and (46) ensures that the operator \hat{O} preserve the symmetry, because while applying it on either state (1,2) or (2,1) leaves the state unchanged. Either the state $|\psi_{12}\rangle$ or $|\psi_{21}\rangle$ do not lost its structure while undergoes through the operation \hat{O} . Let multiply the Eq (45) from both side by the operator \hat{O} , we get

$$\hat{O}\hat{O}|\psi_{12}\rangle = O|\psi_{21}\rangle \quad (47)$$

Putting the value from Eq (46) in Eq. (47) we get

$$\hat{O}\hat{O}|\psi_{12}\rangle = |\psi_{12}\rangle \quad (48)$$

$$\hat{O}^2|\psi_{12}\rangle = |\psi_{12}\rangle \quad (49)$$

Transferring the terms to R.H.S, we get

$$\hat{O}^2|\psi_{12}\rangle - |\psi_{12}\rangle = 0 \quad (50)$$

$$(\hat{O}^2 - I)|\psi_{12}\rangle = 0 \quad (51)$$

Here $|\psi_{12}\rangle \neq 0$, so

$$(\hat{O}^2 - I) = 0 \quad (52)$$

Which implies,

$$\hat{O}^2 = I \quad (53)$$

So, the operator \hat{O} which satisfy the property obtained in Eq.(53) will always preserve the symmetry. Let find out what are the operators which satisfy the property obtained in Eq. (53). Let start from the properties of a unitary matrix.

$$UU^\dagger = U^\dagger U = I \quad (54)$$

and Unitary matrix has (absolute determinant)always equal to 1. so,

$$||U|| = 1 \quad (55)$$

lets return to the Eq. (53), we can get

$$\hat{O}\hat{O} = I \quad (56)$$

Taking the determinant on both te sides, we get

$$|\hat{O}\hat{O}| = |I| \quad (57)$$

It is known that $|AB| = |A||B|$, so, we can obtain

$$|\hat{O}||\hat{O}| = |I| \quad (58)$$

$$|\hat{O}|^2 = 1 \quad (59)$$

$$|\hat{O}| = \pm 1 \quad (60)$$

Considering the absolute value,

$$||\hat{O}|| = 1 \quad (61)$$

Here, we obtained the result that operator \hat{O} satisfy the property of Unitary matrix, hence the operator \hat{O} is a unitary matrix, which preserve the exchange symmetry (Hence Proved). Now lets look again on the operator, can it may be Hermitian as well. We know the property of a Hermitian matrix as follows

$$H^\dagger = H \quad (62)$$

Lets check does operator \hat{O} satisfy this property,

$$\hat{O}^\dagger = \hat{O} \quad (63)$$

Since we already got the information that \hat{O} is unitary, so it must satisfy the condition given in Eq. (54)

$$\hat{O}\hat{O}^\dagger = \hat{O}^\dagger\hat{O} = I \quad (64)$$

From Eq. (56), we know $\hat{O}\hat{O} = I$, so put this in Eq. (64), We obtain

$$\hat{O}\hat{O}^\dagger = \hat{O}^\dagger\hat{O} = \hat{O}\hat{O} \quad (65)$$

Which leads

$$\hat{O}\hat{O}^\dagger = \hat{O}\hat{O} \quad (66)$$

Finally the following can be obtained,

$$\hat{O}^\dagger = \hat{O} \quad (67)$$

Here, we have proved that \hat{O} is also Hermitian matrix, which preserve the exchange symmetry. We have proved that the operator \hat{O} is Unitary and Hermitian both, which preserve the exchange symmetry. Here it is mentioned that, all the Pauli operators are both Unitary and well as Hermitian and these preserve the Exchange symmetry in two qubits.

III. CONCLUSION

In this short note, we have shown that the exchange symmetry is preserved under the unitary and hermitian operations. We have shown simple proofs and also indicated that the Pauli operators also preserve the permutation symmetry in two qubits. We are in hope the presented simple proofs are helpful for the quantum information community and we also foresee the extension

of the work soon in many perspectives on permutation symmetry.

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